

Development of a Rapid and “Open Source” Method to Render a Non-Destructive Image of the Soil Compaction.

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Introduction

On intensive agricultural production areas, building linear infrastructures as natural gas pipeline may have a real impact on soil properties and crops yields. So, for many years, the “*Chambre d’agriculture de la Somme*” has followed each big worksite building underground gas pipeline or electric power lines. After the worksite, in partnership with the owner of the infrastructure, field measurements are made during three years on some fields to assess the impact of the worksite and how the soil recovers its potential. One of those measurements consists in analysing soil compaction. But as we need to observe the soil compaction each year at the same place, a non-destructive method has to be used. So, an electronic penetrometer is used in substitution or in addition to the “*profil cultural*” method (Boizard, 2017). But the penetrometer doesn’t provide any “picture” of the soil. It only gives the penetration resistance (Shothorst, 1968) data on each dot. The main idea is that a 2D image of the soil would be better to analyse the compaction on each part of the worksite (trench, trail ...) and on control zone. The aim of this article is to explain a quite easy way to render the data of the penetrometer to a very simple 2D image of the soil compaction called “Interpolated Penetrometric Soil Profile”.

Material and method

To collect data on the field, an electronic penetrometer is used. The equipment is an “Eijkelpkamp Penetrologger” which records data from 0 to 80cm depth with an accuracy of 1cm and an accuracy of 1N for the strength (i.e. 0.01MPa for a cone surface of 1cm²) This device is delivered with a software to draw a graph showing resistance as a function of depth for each point and export these data as a text file (.TXT). In our context, a precise localization of the measures is needed. So a corrected GPS is used to set up the measurements every year at the same place. Field measurements are made between October and March, while the soil is maintained at field capacity. Measuring points are marked perpendicular to the linear infrastructure. So each zone of the worksite (trench, trail, soil storage ...) and a control zone outside of the worksite are observed. 12 measurements are made every meter along 11 m (from 0 to 11) for a classical worksite or 16 measures every 2 meters along 30 m (from 0 to 30) for large worksites. Each measurement is repeated 4 times spaced 2 meters. The data are analysed with a spreadsheet and R software. For each measure there are 81 values (every centimetre from 0 to 80). An average of the 4 repeated values is calculated for every measure. Empty values are filled with the last value upper and the spreadsheet is presented as a matrix of 3 columns: X (from 1 to 12), Y (from 0 to 80) and the average value. The 972 (12*81) values are not sufficient to have a smooth and “natural” image of the soil profile. So the values are interpolated, with R, between 1 and 12 (i.e. the width) with a step of 0.125 (every 12.5cm) and between 0 and 80 (i.e. the depth) with a step of 0.5 (every 0.5cm). So the final dataset is populated with 14329 values (89*161). The interpolation is calculated with the “*akima*” library of R and the “*interp*” command:

```
>interp(x, y, z, xo=seq(1,12,by=0.125), yo=seq(-80,0, by=0.5), linear =FALSE,
extrap=TRUE, duplicate = "median", dupfun = NULL)
```

With x = ID of the measure; y = depth of the value*-1 and z = average value.

The final dataset is used to render an image with R and the “*image*” command which produces a “heatmap” where the different kinds of resistance are represented by different shades of blue (for the most friable zone) to green, yellow or red (for the most compacted zone).

Figure 1: Interpreted IPSP

Results and discussion

With such an image of the soil resistance, it’s quite easy to see where the problems are. The correlation between the location of the resistant zones and the compacted zones has been demonstrated the “*profil cultural*” method during and after the worksite. Just like traffic lights, the colours indicate the depth and the width of the resistant and friable zones. So one can take a decision: - Is it necessary to have a deep soil tillage to break up the compacted zones? – With which equipment? Obviously, the accuracy of this method is not sufficient to describe the compaction as precisely as the “*profil cultural*” and how the soil is recovering a natural state. But, within less than 2 hours, an assessment of the soil over more than 20 m width can be made without digging a single hole. Moreover, by measuring over time, it’s possible to evaluate the evolution of the soil structure.

Conclusion

A little picture is better than a long discussion. With the Interpolated Penetrometric Soil Profile, the “*Chambre d’agriculture de la Somme*” has a tool to explain easily the consequences of a worksite for the soil, even to people who have no agronomic training. The possibility to compare exactly the same place before and after a soil tillage or year after year without spending too much time is a competitive advantage of this method. With enough images of the same place, why not considering a film afterwards?!

References

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